

Vol. 16**49. BLAST analysis of the terminal sequences of cloned markers from the genetic map of rice**

S. CONSTANTINO, A. RESURRECCION, B. ALBANO, J.-A. CHAMPOUX, C. VILLAREAL, G.S. KHUSH and J. BENNETT

Division of Plant Breeding, Genetics and Biochemistry, International Rice Research Institute, MCPO 3127, Makati City 1271, Philippines

Functional genomics seeks to assign biological function to the sequences of genes and intergenic regions. This assignment may be accomplished by forward genetics, reverse genetics or a variety of ancillary approaches. Experience shows that a large minority (25-42%) of anonymous gene sequences from a plant such as rice have sufficient sequence similarity to already characterized genes from rice or other organisms, that a reasonable inference can be made as to the class of protein encoded by the gene (Uchimiya *et al.* 1992, Yamamoto and Sasaki 1997, Harushima *et al.* 1998). While this sort of analysis usually falls short of establishing biological function, it can provide important clues, especially when combined with the location of the gene on a genetic or physical map of rice (Harushima *et al.* 1998). It is for this reason that we have attempted to provide sequence data for 350 of the markers of the genetic map established principally by workers from Cornell University (McCouch *et al.* 1988, Causse *et al.* 1994). These data supplement the large database assembled from sequenced markers of the genetic map developed by the Rice (Genome Research Project at Tsukuba (Harushima *et al.* 1998).

Terminal sequencing was conducted principally on both RZ clones (cDNA clones derived from RNA of etiolated leaves of IR36) and RG clones (genomic clones derived from IR36 DNA). Some barley (BCD) and oat (CDO) cDNA clones were also sequenced. The names and map locations of these clones are presented in Robeniol *et al.* (1996), which also describes the manual sequencing procedure. Both ends of each clone were sequenced to allow PCR-based amplification of longer DNA segments than is possible with data derived from the single-pass sequencing conducted by Uchimiya *et al.* (1992) and Harushima *et al.* (1998). The nucleotide sequences and the deduced amino acid sequences of each terminus were then compared to the Genbank databases using programs of the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) (Altschul *et al.* 1990). Table 1 shows hits with the BLAST-N program accessed through the Entrez Web site at www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov.

A total of 76 clones, representing all twelve rice chromosomes, recorded hits on known sequences. The termini of each clone were designated as F or R depending on whether they were sequenced using the universal forward (F) or reverse (R) sequencing primer. As all inserts had been ligated into the vectors in random orientation, there was no relationship between the F and R ends and the direction of transcription of the gene. Most of the hits (71%) were among the RZ clones, consistent with these clones being from a cDNA library (Causse *et al.* 1994). Relative few hits (24%) were found among the RG clones which were random *Pst*I genomic clones. The remainder (5%) were BCD and CDO cDNA clones. In 20% of the 76 clones registering hits, both termini hit on known genes, and in all of these cases the same class of protein was revealed, even if the name was different, as in the case of RZ244. For this clone, the F terminus hit ferric leghemoglobin reductase and the R terminus hit lipoamide dehydrogenase but these proteins have the same function and in soybean nodules are probably the same proteins. For the remaining 80% of clones, only the F or R terminus hit on a known gene. The usual reason for the lack of homology at the other terminus was that the terminus corresponded to a poorly conserved region of the gene such

as the 3'-untranslated region.

Most of the hits were to rice and other plant genes and were unequivocal, including 19 hits on genes known only from dicotyledonous plants. Three hits were to non-plant genes (maize dwarf mottle virus coat protein, *Caenorhabditis dolichol* monophosphate mannose synthase, human isovaleryl CoA dehydrogenase). Further sequencing would be required to confirm these particular hits. The hits included several cases in which more than one member of a gene family was revealed. Alpha-tubulin was found on chromosomes 1 and 3, ferredoxin III on chromosomes 2 and 3, and cytosolic glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) on chromosomes 4 (twice) and 8. Translational elongation factors were found on chromosomes 2, 3 and 12. As further genes of known function are isolated and deposited in the public databases, the number of hits registered by the 350 clones markers listed by Robeniol *et al.* (1996) is expected to increase from the 76 recorded here. In addition, the current hits will be examined more closely to determine their patterns of expression and their biological function in terms of specific traits.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported in part by grants from the Rockefeller Foundation and the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation (BMZ).

Table 1. Rice, oat and barley DNA sequences with significant homology to known genes

Chr	Locl	Putative Identification	Score	Organism	Chr	Locl	Putative Identification	Score	Organism
1	RZ566 F	metallothionine	231	rice		RZ244 R	lipamide dehydrogenase	431	soybean
	RZ566 R	metallothionine	565	rice	5	RZ390 F	cytochrome b5	1,035	rice
1	RZ836 F	α -tubulin (RIP3)	194	rice	5	RZ455 R	GTP binding protein	184	tomato
	RZ836 R	α -tubulin (RIP3)	468	rice	5	CDO580 R	isovaleryl coA dehydrogenase	446	human
1	RZ588 R	β -ketoacyl-ACP synthase	748	castor bean	6	RZ508 F	catalase	1,095	rice
1	RZ730 R	ubiquitin conjugate enzyme	372	maize		RZ508 R	catalase	516	rice
1	RZ744R	B2 protein	236	carrot	6	RG64 F	blast resistance clone	1,051	rice
1	RG345 F	peptidase of D1 protein	155	barley		RG64 R	blast resistance clone	891	rice
1	RZ382 R	coat protein of dwarf mottle virus	180	maize DM virus	6	RZ140 F	homeobox protein	524	tomato
1	RG233 F	enoyl-CoA hydratase	323	Arabidopsis	6	RZ22X R	human PRP8 protein	330	human
	RG233 R	FeS cluster assembly gene	233	Azotobacter	6	RZ405 R	high affinity K transporter	475	wheat
1	BCD828 R	mitochondrial ATP-2F1-ATPase	665	wheat	6	RZ682 R	nodulation protein nodK	296	<i>E. coli</i>
2	RZ204 F	mitochondrial ATP/ADP translocator	792	rice	7	RZ488 F	mRNA for thioredoxin h	383	rice
	RZ204 R	mitochondrial ATP/ADP translocator	1,160	rice		RZ488 R	mRNA for thioredoxin h	307	rice
2	RZ643 F	ferredoxin III	160	maize	7	RZ509 R	bpw1 water transport protein	135	barley
2	RZ643 R	ferredoxin III	519	maize	7	RG128 F	mRNA for acyl-(acyl protein) thioesterase	165	Arabidopsis
2	RZ962 F	ribosomal protein L17a	223	rice	7	RG156 F	rat cytomegalovirus DNA biosynthetic enzyme	164	rat virus
2	RZ962 R	ribosomal protein L17a	848	rice	8	RZ143 F	cytosolic GADPH	655	rice
2	RZ273 R	mitochondrial ATP/ADP translocator	539	rice	8	RZ617 F	poly-A binding protein	680	wheat
2	RZ876 F	EF-tuf a	712	soybean	8	RZ649 F	fructose diphosphate aldolase	336	rice
2	RZ87 R	ATP dependent protease ClpC	173	tomato	8	RZ997 F	plastidic Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase	487	rice
2	RG256 F	plastidic aspartate amino transferase	661	Panicum		RZ997 R	plastidic Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase	974	rice
2	RG120 F	DNA repair protein	228	mouse	8	RZ572 F	cytosolic APX	294	maize
2	RZ476 R	EF-gamma	483	Arabidopsis	8	RG20 F	meristem L1 layer homeobox protein	265	Arabidopsis
2	RG322 R	DNA binding protein	161	pea	8	RZ698 F	plastidic Pi/PEP transporter	313	maize
3	RZ16 F	ascorbate peroxidase	231	rice		RZ698 R	plastid Pi/PEP transporter	641	maize
	RZ16 R	ascorbate peroxidase	887	rice	9	RZ792 F	nucleic acid binding protein	269	maize
3	RZ589 F	α -tubulin (RIP3)	348	rice	9	CDO590 R	protein phosphatase	523	tobacco
	RZ589 R	α -tubulin (RIP3)	730	rice	9	RZ206 F	VDAC protein/porin	325	wheat
3	RG754 F	phosphoglycerate mutase	261	maize	9	RZ228 F	HSP82	650	rice
	RG754 R	phosphoglycerate mutase	393	ricinus	9	RZ 337 R	suppressor-like protein	431	Arabidopsis
3	RZ142 F	dolichol monophosphate mannose synthase	50	Caenorhabditis	10	RZ500 R	sugar transporter	379	Arabidopsis
3	RZ448 R	phosphoglucomutase	870	maize	10	RZ561 F	cell division cycle protein cDc48 mRNA	393	Arabidopsis
3	RZ576 F	plastidic ribosomal protein	542	Arabidopsis	10	RZ892 R	alanine amino transferase	787	Panicum
3	RZ585 F	Histone H3	194	rice	10	RZ400 F	GTP binding protein	657	lotus
3	RZ614 F	ferredoxin III	181	maize	10	RZ536 R	rubisco activase	716	rice
3	RZ574 R	cell wall protein	216	Arabidopsis	11	RZ900 F	S-adenosyl homocysteine dehydratase	746	<i>C. roseus</i>
3	RG179 F	UDPG dehydrogenase	484	soybean	11	RG247 F	peptide transporter	176	barley
3	RG418X F	KAT C/KAT A kinesin	254	Arabidopsis	11	RG118 R	exon of ACC oxidase	158	apple
3	RZ993X F	EF-1 α	135	rice	11	RZ737 F	lipid transfer protein	1,071	rice
4	RZ740 F	S-adenosyl methionine decarboxylase	811	rice	12	RG218 F	β -ketoacyl CoA synthase	201	<i>S. chinensis</i>
4	CDO1328 F	GADPH (pseudogene)	227	maize	12	RZ261 F	dehydroquininate dehydratase	299	tobacco
4	RZ86 F	cytosolic GADPH	716	barley	12	RZ397 F	glutathione-S-transferase	216	wheat
4	RZ250 R	molybdenum co-factor biosynthetic enzyme	355	Arabidopsis	12	RG396 R	plastidic transketolase	484	potato
4	RG449 F	serine/threonine protein kinase	190	Arabidopsis	12	RZ993X F	EF-1 α	125	rice
5	RZ244 F	ferric leghemoglobin reductase	48	soybean					

Reference

Altschul, S. F., W. Gish, W. Miller, Webb, E.W. Myers and D.J. Lipmann, 1990. Basic Local Alignment Search Tool. *Mol. Biol.* 215: 403-410.

Causse, MA., T.M. Fulton, Y.G. Cho, S.N. Ahn, J. Chunwongse, K.Wu, J. Xiao, Z. Yu, P.C. Ronald, S.B. Harrington, GA. Second, SR. McCouch and S.D. Tanksley, 1994. Saturated molecular map of the rice Genome based on an interspecific backcross population. *Genetics* 138: 1251-1274.

Harushima, Y., M. Yano, A. Shomura, M. Sato, T. Shimano, Y. Kuboki, T. Yamamoto, S.Y. Lin, B.A Antonio, A. Parco, H. Kajiya, N. Huang, K. Yamamoto, Y. Nagamura, N. Kurata, G.S. Khush and T. Sasaki, 1998. A high-density rice genetic linkage map with 2275 markers using a single F₂ population. *Genetics* 148: 479-494.

McCouch, S.R., G. Kochert, Z.H. Yu, Z.Y. Wang, G.S. Khush, W.R. Coffman and S.D. Tanksley, 1988. Molecular mapping of rice chromosomes. *Theor. Appl Genet.* 76: 815-829.

Robeniol, J.A., S.V. Constantino, A.P. Resurreccion, C.P. Villareal, B. Ghareyazie, B.R. Lu, S.K. Katiyar, C.A. Menguito, E.R. Angeles, H.-Y. Fu, S. Reddy, W. Park, S.R. McCouch, G.S. Khush and J. Bennett, 1996. Sequence-tagged sites and low-cost DNA markers for rice. *Proceedings of the Third International Rice Genetics Symposium.* p. 293-306.

Uchimiya H., S. Kiduo, T. Shimazaki, S. Aotsuka, S. Takamatsu, R. Nishi, H. Hashimoto, Y. Matsubayashi, N. Kiduo, M. Umeda and A. Kato, 1992. Random sequencing of cDNA libraries reveals a variety of expressed genes in cultured cells of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) *Plant Journal.* 106:1241-1255.

Yamamoto, K. and T. Sasaki, 1997. Large scale EST sequencing in rice. *Plant Mol. Biol.* 35: 135-144.

Vol. 16